

DEFINITION OF CONCEPTUAL METAPHOR AND ITS TYPES

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Annotation: The article deals with the definition of conceptual metaphor. It also reveals the types of conceptual metaphor and examples for each type.

Key words: rhetorical devices, resemblance metaphors, structure metaphor, orientational metaphor, ontological metaphor.

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОЙ МЕТАФОРЫ И ЕЕ ТИПОВ

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается определение концептуальной метафоры. В нем также раскрываются типы концептуальных метафор и примеры для каждого типа.

Ключевые слова: риторические приемы, метафоры сходства, структурная метафора, ориентационная метафора, онтологическая метафора.

What is conceptual metaphor? How it began to develop? What are the types of conceptual metaphor?

Before answering these questions, we are going to investigate the definition of metaphor itself. The notion "metaphor" was first established in ancient Greece, and was focused on practical instruction in how to persuade listeners of a particular point of view by the use of rhetorical devices. Due to its central importance, metaphor came to be known as the master trope. Within this approach, metaphor was characterized by the schematic form: A is B. Most sayings, daily expressions were built based on metaphor. For example, in saying "love is a battlefield," the meaning is love is difficult and dangerous like being on a battlefield in war.

As a consequence, metaphor has been identified since the time of Aristotle with implicit comparison. In other words, while metaphor is based on the comparison of two categories, the comparison is not explicitly marked. This contrasts with simile, where the comparison is overtly

signalled by the use of as or like: love is as difficult as battlefield, love is difficult, like a battlefield in war. Clearly, examples of metaphor like In saying love is a battlefield are based on comparison.

However, sometimes metaphor can be created based on resemblance between two comparing things. Metaphors of this kind are called resemblance metaphors (Grady 1999) Resemblance metaphors based on physical resemblance have been called image metaphors. For example, "the leaves waved in the wind", "the ocean heaved a sigh". Both instances are not mentally true in reality, but the movement of leaves and ocean have an analogy to refer to these motions.

Metaphor is regarded as a cognitive mechanism, a way of thinking and one of the fundamental processes of human cognition, a specific way of conceptualizing information based on the mental process of analogy and knowledge transfer from one conceptual field into another.

Conceptual Metaphor Theory was first proposed by G. Lacoff and M. Johnson in their revolutionary work "Metaphors We Live By" (1980) and since then has been learned and investigated in a number of subsequent researches (Turner, 1991; Kövecses, 2000; Gibbs, 1994; Reddy, 1979). The basic principle of Conceptual Metaphor Theory is that metaphor is not simply a stylistic device: it is a way of thinking, a tool of cognition. According to some scholars the thought itself is fundamentally metaphorical in nature. Metaphor operates at the level of thinking as "our conceptual system is largely metaphorical, and our ordinary conceptual systems, in terms of which we both think and act, is fundamentally metaphorical in nature" (Lacoff, Johnson, 1980, p.3).

As most researchers studied the notion "conceptual metaphor", there is not exact number of types of metaphor. However, according to G. Lacoff and M. Johnson, there are four types distinguished in the Conceptual Metaphor typology.

First type of metaphor is structure metaphor which is created with the reference of the metaphorical and structural organization of one concept (often an abstract one) in terms of another (often a more concrete one). In this case, the source domains provide frameworks for the target domains (Time is Money; Life is Journey)

In order to illustrate how the event structure metaphor applies, consider the specific metaphor LIFE IS A JOURNEY.

This is illustrated by the following examples

STATES ARE LOCATIONS

He's at a crossroads in his life.

CHANGE IS MOTION

He went from his forties to his fifties without a hint of a mid-life crisis.

CAUSES ARE FORCES

He got a head start in life.

PURPOSES ARE DESTINATIONS

I can't ever seem to get to where I want to be in life.

MEANS ARE PATHS

He followed an unconventional course during his life.

Another example for structure metaphor: TIME IS MONEY

You are WASTING MY TIME

This gadget will SAVE YOU HOURS

I DON'T HAVE THE TIME TO GIVE you

How do you SPEND YOUR TIME these days?

I've INVESTED A LOT OF TIME IN her
I don't have ENOUGH TIME TO SPARE for that
You're RUNNING OUT OF TIME
You need to BUDGET YOUR TIME

Second type of metaphor is orientational metaphor. An orientational metaphor is a metaphor (or figurative comparison) that involves spatial relationships (such as up-down, left-right, in-out, on-off, and front-back). Orientational metaphor (a figure that "organizes a whole system of concepts with respect to one another") is one of the three overlapping categories of conceptual metaphors identified by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson in "Metaphors We Live By" (1980). All the following concepts are characterized by an 'upward' orientation, while their 'opposites' receive a 'downward' orientation.

More is up; less is down: Speak up, please. Keep your voice down, please.
Healthy is up; sick is down: Lazarus rose from the dead. He fell ill.
Conscious is up; unconscious is down: Wake up. He sank into a coma.
Control is up; lack of control is down: I'm on top of the situation. He is under my control.
Happy is up; sad is down: I'm feeling up today. He's really low these days.

Third type of conceptual metaphor is an ontological metaphor?

"In general, ontological metaphors enable us to see more sharply delineated structure where there is very little or none ... We can perceive of personification as a form of ontological metaphor. In personification, human qualities are given to nonhuman entities. Personification is very common in literature, but it also abounds in everyday discourse, as the examples below show:

His theory explained to me the behavior of chickens raised in factories.
Life has cheated me.
Inflation is eating up our profits.
Cancer finally caught up with him.
The computer went dead on me.

Theory, life, inflation, cancer, computer are not humans, but they are given qualities of human beings, such as explaining, cheating, eating, catching up, and dying. Personification makes use of one of the best source domains we have--ourselves. In personifying nonhumans as humans, we can begin to understand them a little better."

(Zoltán Kövecses, *Metaphor: A Practical Introduction*. Oxford University Press, 2002)

Lakoff and Johnson on the Various Purposes of Ontological Metaphors

"Ontological metaphors serve various purposes, and the various kinds of metaphors there are reflect the kinds of purposes served. Take the experience of rising prices, which can be metaphorically viewed as an entity via the noun inflation. This gives us a way of referring to the experience:

INFLATION IS AN ENTITY
Inflation is lowering our standard of living.
If there's much more inflation, we'll never survive.
We need to combat inflation.

Inflation is backing us into a corner.

Inflation is taking its toll at the checkout counter and the gas pump.

Buying land is the best way of dealing with inflation.

Inflation makes me sick.

In conclusion, cognitive Linguistics has developed a new approach to the problem of metaphor and has introduced the notion of conceptual (cognitive) metaphor, regarded as a cognitive mechanism, one of the fundamental processes of human cognition, a specific way of conceptualizing information based on the mental process of analogy and knowledge transfer from one conceptual field into another;

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